

Ultrasonic waves and temperature effects on graphene structure fabricated by electrochemical exfoliation method

R. Bakhshandeh¹, [Azizollah Shafiekhani](#)^{1,2}

¹ Department of Physics, Faculty of Physics and Chemistry, Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran..

² School of Physics, Institute for Research in Fundamental Sciences, P.O. Box 19395-5531, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

It is a challenge to fabricate high-quality graphene sheets due to the different effects of external factors on the fabrication process. Ultrasonic waves and temperature can be used as two important external factors to fabricate graphene. We conducted a research to study the effects of ultrasonic waves and temperature on the graphene fabrication process. To show the effects of the external factors on graphene sheets, we fabricated three samples. The first sample has been fabricated using electrochemical exfoliation method without applying any external factors. To fabricate two other samples, we used the same fabrication method but applying ultrasonic waves and temperature to homogenize the electrolyte. Second sample has been fabricated using 420 W ultrasonic waves. To fabricate third sample, 100 °C temperature has been applied to the electrolyte using heater stirrer. We studied the three fabricated samples using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, ultraviolet–visible, X-Ray diffraction, Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and Scanning electron microscope and Transmission electron microscopy. As a result of this research, we found that applying ultrasonic waves to homogenize the electrolyte during the fabrication process plays an important role to decrease oxygen groups and increase IG to ID rate in graphene structure.

Keywords: Electrochemical exfoliation, Graphene, Temperature, Ultrasonic wave.